

Harmonizing the Living Lab Language: Towards a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

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Abstract

With Living Lab (LL) research and infrastructures supported by LLs increasing exponentially over the past two decades, there is a need for clear and fluid language, understanding and communication among the LL communities and all those who come into contact with LLs. We present a 'Research in progress paper' detailing the steps (term identification, definition(s) selection and validation through internal and external consensus) in the creation of an open access dynamic Living Lab Lexicon.

Key words

Living Lab, Lexicon, Terminology, Communication, Harmonization

Introduction

The first descriptions/definitions of Living Labs (LL), as environments for designing, developing, testing and evaluating communication technologies and services in early stages of the innovation or as a user-centric research methodology for sensing, prototyping, validating and refining complex solutions in multiple and evolving real-life contexts, appear in 2005 (Pierson & Lievens 2005; Eriksson et al., 2005). Since then, a number of definitions have surfaced, providing variations on main themes describing Living Labs, such as: user-centric environments for open innovation (Schaffers et al, 2007), collaborations of public-private-civic partnerships (Feurstein et al, 2008), platforms with shared resources (Leminen et al., 2017), to name a few. The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), describes LLs as open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation activities in communities, placing citizens at the center of innovation.” LLs focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.

In 2020, the Horizon Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure (VITALISE) project brought a new era to LL Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) services by introducing the LLs as Research Infrastructures (RIs). VITALISE aims to strengthen the LLs position in the worldwide RIs roadmap by assembling and harmonizing processes, procedures and tools across the European Living Labs including some Canadian Living Labs. This collectively espoused endeavour is ultimately leading to effective and fluid access for researchers, as well as knowledge transfer and exchange among LLs centered on the health and well-being domain.

As European LLs gathered around the main theme of harmonization, it became clear that one of the first activities that would help ensure fluid and transparent communication would be the establishment of a ‘common language and terminology’. Indeed, even though the VITALISE consortium members all have extensive experience in LL methodology and research, the ‘language’ and terms used did not always refer to the same concepts, even if the core meaning was often similar. As one can imagine, this sometimes led to confusion and misunderstandings that became even more apparent when talking to different ‘players’ within the LL communities that are not part of VITALISE. This became even more pronounced when interacting with individuals who are novices or those completely outside the LL community. With the overall vision to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different

‘players’ within the LL communities and all those who come in contact with LLs, we decided to create a VITALISE Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) where LL key terms are identified, defined, and shared with the LL community and beyond. During this process we also remain mindful that certain terms have variations in meaning depending on the context in which they are used.

The Current Project

To respond to this challenge, we assembled a team of VITALISE researchers from European and Canadian LLs. The team was supported by external experts in the fields of linguistics and psycholinguistics, as well as by a medical librarian.

Objectives

The following five (5) objectives were pursued:

1. Determine and select which LL terms to define.
2. Identify already existing definitions.
3. Consider who the target audience(s) is (are). What are their potential backgrounds? Consider having a primary definition for each term and potentially a secondary or tertiary definition based on context and the user.
4. Establish a process that will result in the definitions that we propose for the selected terms.
5. Propose definitions for the terms selected within a framework representing the LL process and reality.

Methods and Preliminary Findings

In addressing the first objective, we began with a small number of terms which were nevertheless representative of the most frequently used terms in Living Lab research. To avoid selection bias, we opted for a systematic search through the literature to create a corpus of articles containing relevant terms. A health sciences librarian conducted a multi-file search of MEDLINE, EMBASE, and PsycInfo on the Ovid platform using the syntax (Living adj1 lab*).mp. on August 12, 2022. The search found 854 citations across the three databases; duplicates were removed using the Ovid platform, leaving 567 unique citations. These were imported into Rayyan, a screening platform often used in Scoping or Systematic Reviews (Ouzzani et al., 2016). At this point, for articles to be considered for inclusion in the corpus, they had to have been published in 2008 or later and to have utilized a Living Lab methodology or to have included key words such as

“living labs, co-creation, real life settings, user centered, interactive exchange, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research, innovation, users as partners, controlled environment, participatory design” in the abstract or the keywords provided in the article. Furthermore, articles had to have at least an abstract in English or French. Following a similar selection process to the one used in scoping reviews, two reviewers judged the eligibility of each citation. The Rayyan platform also allows one to vote on eligibility of an article to either: 1) Include (if relevant), 2) Maybe Include, or 3) Exclude if not relevant. The majority of citations also provided a full pdf of the article. Of the 567 articles initially entered, 173 were initially included, 340 were excluded, and 54 were in the ‘Maybe’ category. For those articles assigned to the ‘Maybe’ category, a third reviewer resolved conflicts.

In addition to the articles identified by the search above, we also added the papers included in the proceedings of the ENoLL Open Living Lab Days (2013-2022). Articles selected from the two sources, the literature and the ENoLL proceedings were treated as two separate corpora and the ensuing analysis was also conducted separately in order to avoid bias.

At a second step we compiled the list of articles and ENoLL papers and downloaded all the pdfs into Word Stat, a word mining software (Provalis Research). Using WordStat, we calculated frequency of occurrence and percent of occurrence for single word terms (e.g. user), for two-word terms (e.g. real life) and for three-word terms (e.g. technology innovation management). These counts were calculated separately for the articles identified from the literature and for those obtained from the ENoLL proceedings. When we compared the two sets of data, we observed that there were minor differences and thus proceeded to consider them as one set. Table 1 presents the top ten (10) terms identified from the articles and ENoLL papers combined.

Table 1. Top 1-word, 2-word, and 3-word terms

	FREQUENCY	NO. CASES	% CASES	LENGTH	TF • IDF
LIVING	14389	341	98%	1	127,0
INNOVATION	8625	314	90%	1	385,1
LAB	8366	332	95%	1	171,0
RESEARCH	8078	334	96%	1	144,1
LABS	6389	297	85%	1	439,7
DESIGN	4814	310	89%	1	241,7
USER	4420	292	84%	1	336,8
SOCIAL	4292	317	91%	1	173,9
PROJECT	4201	311	89%	1	205,1
USERS	3960	285	82%	1	343,5
	FREQUENCY	NO. CASES	% CASES	LENGTH	TF • IDF
LIVING LAB	7223	326	94%	2	204,9
LIVING LABS	5678	293	84%	2	424,2
OPEN INNOVATION	1184	182	52%	2	333,3
OLDER ADULTS	964	70	20%	2	671,4
REAL LIFE	739	196	56%	2	184,2
CASE STUDY	645	169	49%	2	202,3
END USERS	635	146	42%	2	239,5
LONG TERM	584	156	45%	2	203,5
HEALTH CARE	562	98	28%	2	309,3
INNOVATION MANAGEMENT	559	146	42%	2	210,9
	FREQUENCY	NO. CASES	% CASES	LENGTH	TF • IDF
URBAN LIVING LABS	377	72	21%	3	258
TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION MANAGEMENT	317	115	33%	3	152,4
URBAN LIVING LAB	142	49	14%	3	120,9
OPEN INNOVATION NETWORKS	124	45	13%	3	110,2
BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS	104	15	4%	3	142
USER CENTRED DESIGN	91	55	16%	3	72,9
LIVING LAB SERVICES	73	9	3%	3	115,9
PUBLIC SECTOR INNOVATION	65	8	2%	3	106,5
LIVING LAB NETWORKS	64	32	9%	3	66,3
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS	57	25	7%	3	65,2

At a third step, and following a consensus process, we selected the top 50 terms with regard to frequency of occurrence and % of occurrence across the different corpora. These would be the first terms that would be defined. We then proceeded to search for existing definitions in the literature. In parallel, a concept map was created, and a subset of the selected terms was mapped onto the concept map, as seen below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. First draft of the Living Lab concept map with terms

Working within the principles of the LL methodology, we used an iterative approach of consultation in small group and then in a larger working group attended by VITALISE LL researchers during a working session where the goal was to examine/debate existing definitions for suitability and appropriateness, identify new concepts linked to the chosen terms, discuss them and arrive at a consensus that resulted in maintaining some of the original definitions and altering others. For example, for the term ‘Co-creation’ the original definition that appears on the graph was changed to: Creating new value for and with the relevant stakeholders in a collaborative process. We also added the most recent revision of the definition of ‘living lab’ from ENoLL.

We then proceeded to work on the Stakeholder typology. Following discussion and consensus the following changes were made as shown below in bold: Stakeholder typology was replaced by Stakeholder involvement and two new categories were added.

- Lead user
- End-user
- **Consumer became Customer**
- Expert
- Non user
- **Target user**
- **Early adopter**

During the same working session a new concept map was created, comprising the changes proposed by the group (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Most recent Living Lab Concept map with terms

Conclusion and Next Steps

While several LL terms have already been defined and validated there are several other terms pertaining to living labs and to the living lab methodology for which definitions need to be identified and validated. These include terms already identified and presented in the VITALISE deliverable D4.5 Living Lab Guidelines (first version). Furthermore, the variety of concepts associated with LLs operating in diverse environments will be explored. As a further step we will seek to obtain feedback on all of these terms and definitions from a larger pool of 'LLabers' outside the VITALISE consortium, as well as from novices in the LL experience. This will allow us to obtain external validity on the set of definitions. In parallel we will also seek feedback from other groups of potential users (Academia, Industry, Government, Citizens), to ensure that the definitions included in the Living Lab Lexicon will reflect the diversity of context and use. In the end, all feedback and information will be compiled and imported in what will become an Open Access Dynamic Living Lab Lexicon.

Funding

This research was funded by VITALISE - Virtual health and wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure- funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union for Research Innovation. Grant agreement number: 101007990

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